

Multiplicative Interpretation of Neutrosophic Cubic Set on B-Algebra

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Abstract

Purpose of this paper is to interpret the multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set. Here we define the notation of \varkappa -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set and study it with the help of neutrosophic cubic M-subalgebra, neutrosophic cubic normal ideal and neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideal. We also study \varkappa -multiplication under homomorphism and cartesian product through significant characteristics.

Keywords: B-algebra, Neutrosophic cubic set, \varkappa -Multiplication, Cartesian product, Homomorphism.

1.Introduction

Theory of existing and non-existing value was first introduced by Zadeh [1,2]. Cubic set was defined by Jun et al. [3] in 2012, which was the modern form of interval-valued fuzzy set. Cubic set with the help of subalgebras, ideals and closed ideals of B -algebra was studied by Senapati et al. [4]. After the defing of BCK -algebra and BCI -algebra by Imai et al. [5] and Iseki [6], cubic set through subalgebras and q -ideals in BCK/BCI -algebra was investigated by Jun et al. [7, 8]. Notion of M -subalgebra on G -algebra is introduced and analyzed by Khalid et al. [9]. Interval-valued fuzzy set on B -algebra was studied by Senapati et al. [10,11]. Intuitionistic fuzzy translation and multiplication of G -algebra were deeply studied by by Khalid et al. [19]. Neutrosophic cubic set is the extended form of interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy theory with indeterminacy was introduced by Smarandache [12]. Neutrosophic logics and neutrosophic probability gave the new idea of research were interpret by Smarandache [13]. Neutrosophic cubic was introduced by Jun et al. [14]. Neutrosophic cubic point, (α, β) -fuzzy ideals and neutrosophic cubic (α, β) -ideals were analyzed by Gulistan et al. [15]. A new idea of normal ideal and closed normal ideal under neutrosophic cubic set was given and investigated by Khalid et al. [16]. Neutrosophic cubic set was investigated by Jun et al. [17]. PS fuzzy ideals were studied by Priya et al. [18]. Rosenfeld's fuzzy subgroup was studied by Biswas [20]. B -homomorphism was deeply studied by Neggers et al. [21]. Neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra was extensively studied by Khalid et al. [22]. A B -algebra is an important logical class of algebra was defined by Neggers et al. [23]. T -Neutrosophic Cubic Set was defined and deeply investigated by Khalid et al. [24].

In this paper, we define \varkappa -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set and investigate the neutrosophic cubic M -subalgebra, neutrosophic cubic normal ideal (NCNID) and neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideal (NCCNID) under \varkappa -multiplication with the help of P -intersection, P -union etc. We also study the cartesian product and

homomorphism of τ -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic normal ideal (τ MNCNID) and τ -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideal (τ MNCCNID) with important results.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [19] A nonempty set X with a constant 0 and $*$ is said to be B -algebra if it fulfills these conditions:

- 1: $t * t = 0$,
- 2: $t * 0 = 0$, for all $t \in X$.
- 3: $(t * t) * t = t * (t * (0 * t)) \forall t, t, t \in X$.

Definition 2.2 [21] A nonempty subset K of B -algebra X is called a subalgebra of Y if $t * t \in K \forall t, t \in K$, a mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ of B -algebra is called B -homomorphism if $f(t * t) = f(t) * f(t) \forall t, t \in X$.

Definition 2.3 [1] Let X be a collection of elements like t . Then a FS J in X is defined as $J = \{ \langle t, v_J(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$, where $\mu_J(t)$ is called the existenceship value of t in J and $v_J(t) \in [0,1]$.

For a family $J_i = \{ \langle t, v_{J_i}(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ of FSs in X , where $i \in k$ and k is index set, Then join (\vee) and meet (\wedge) are as follows:

$$\bigvee_{i \in k} J_i = (\bigvee_{i \in k} v_{J_i})(t) = \sup\{v_{J_i} \mid i \in k\}$$

and

$$\bigwedge_{i \in k} J_i = (\bigwedge_{i \in k} v_{J_i})(t) = \inf\{v_{J_i} \mid i \in k\},$$

respectively, $\forall t \in X$.

Definition 2.4 [2] An IVFS B is of the form $B = \{ \langle t, \tilde{v}_B(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$, where $\tilde{v}_B : X \rightarrow D[0,1]$, here $D[0,1]$ is the collection of all subintervals of $[0,1]$. The intervals $\tilde{v}_B(t) = [v_B^-(t), v_B^+(t)] \forall t \in X$ denote the degree of existence of t to the set B , also $\tilde{v}_B^c = [1 - v_B^-(t), 1 - v_B^+(t)]$ shows the complement of \tilde{v}_B .

For a family $B_i = \{ \langle t, \tilde{v}_{B_i}(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ of IVFSs in X where k is an index set and $i \in k$, the union $G = \bigcup_{i \in k} \tilde{v}_{B_i}(t)$ and the intersection $F = \bigcap_{i \in k} \tilde{v}_{B_i}(t)$ are defined below:

$$G(t) = \text{rsup}\{\tilde{v}_{B_i}(t) \mid i \in k\}$$

and

$$F(t) = \text{rinf}\{\tilde{v}_{B_i}(t) \mid i \in k\},$$

respectively, $\forall t \in X$.

Definition 2.5 [20] Consider two elements $D_1, D_2 \in D[0,1]$. If $D_1 = [t_1^-, t_1^+]$ and $D_2 = [t_2^-, t_2^+]$, then $\text{rmax}(D_1, D_2) = [\max(t_1^-, t_2^-), \max(t_1^+, t_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $D_1 \vee^r D_2$ and $\text{rmin}(D_1, D_2) = [\min(t_1^-, t_2^-), \min(t_1^+, t_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $D_1 \wedge^r D_2$. Thus, if $D_i = [t_i^-, t_i^+] \in D[0,1]$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, then we define $\text{rsup}_i(D_i) = [\sup_i(t_i^-), \sup_i(t_i^+)]$, i. e., $\vee_i^r D_i = [\vee_i t_i^-, \vee_i t_i^+]$. Similarly we define $\text{rinf}_i(D_i) = [\inf_i(t_i^-), \inf_i(t_i^+)]$, i. e., $\wedge_i^r D_i = [\wedge_i t_i^-, \wedge_i t_i^+]$. Now we call $D_1 \geq D_2 \iff t_1^- \geq t_2^-$ and $t_1^+ \geq t_2^+$. Similarly the relations $D_1 \leq D_2$ and $D_1 = D_2$ are defined.

Definition 2.6 [19] A fuzzy set $B = \{ \langle t, v_B(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ is called a fuzzy subalgebra of X if $v_B(t * t) \geq \min\{v_B(t), v_B(t)\} \forall t, t \in X$.

Definition 2.7 [14] Let X be a nonempty set. A NCS is $P_k = (B, \Lambda)$, where $B = \{ \langle t; B_T(t), B_I(t), B_F(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ is an interval neutrosophic set in X and $\Lambda = \{ \langle t; \lambda_T(t), \lambda_I(t), \lambda_F(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ is a neutrosophic set in X .

Definition 2.8 [3] Let U be a universe and cubic set in U , we mean a structure $\{ t, \bar{v}_A(t), \lambda_A(t) \mid t \in U \}$ in which \bar{v}_A is an IVF set in U and λ_A is a fuzzy set in U . A cubic set $A = \{ t, \bar{v}_A(t), \lambda_A(t) \mid t \in U \}$ is simply denoted by $C(U)$, which is the set of all cubic sets in U .

Definition 2.9 [3] Let $C = \{ \langle t, C(t), \lambda(t) \rangle \}$ be a cubic set, where $C(t)$ is an IVFS in Y , $\lambda(t)$ is a fuzzy set in Y . Then A is cubic subalgebra under $*$ if it fulfills these axioms:

$$C1: C(t * t) \geq \text{rmin}\{C(t), C(t)\},$$

$$C2: \lambda(t * t) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda(t), \lambda(t)\} \forall t, t \in X.$$

Definition 2.10 [18] A fuzzy set $B = \{ \langle t, v_B(t) \rangle \mid t \in X \}$ is called a fuzzy ideal of X if

$$(i) v_B(0) \geq v_B(t),$$

$$(ii) v_B(t) \geq \min\{v_B(t * t), v_B(t)\} \forall t, t \in X.$$

Definition 2.11 [14] For any $C_i = (A_i, F_i)$, where $A_i = \{ \langle t; A_{iT}(t), A_{iI}(t), A_{iF}(t) \rangle \mid t \in Y \}$, $F_i = \{ \langle t; F_{iT}(t), F_{iI}(t), F_{iF}(t) \rangle \mid t \in Y \}$ for $i \in k$, then

$$\text{P-union: } \bigcup_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigcup_{i \in k} A_i, \bigvee_{i \in k} F_i),$$

$$\text{P-intersection: } \bigcap_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigcap_{i \in k} A_i, \bigwedge_{i \in k} F_i),$$

$$\text{R-union: } \bigcup_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigcup_{i \in k} A_i, \bigwedge_{i \in k} F_i),$$

$$\text{R-intersection: } \bigcap_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigcap_{i \in k} A_i, \bigvee_{i \in k} F_i).$$

Definition 2.12 [16] A NCS $R = (R_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F})$ of X is called a NCNID of X if it fulfills following axioms:

$$N3. R_{T,I,F}(0) \geq R_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha) \text{ and } \lambda_{T,I,F}(0) \leq \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha),$$

$$N4. R_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha) \geq \text{rmin}\{R_{T,I,F}((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)), R_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\},$$

$$N5. \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha) * (t * \beta), \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\}, \forall t, t \in X \text{ and } \alpha, \beta \in [0,1].$$

Let $R = \{ R_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F} \}$ be a NCS X then it is called NCCNID of X if it fulfills $N4, N5$ and $N6: R_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) \geq R_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha)$ and $\lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) \leq \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \forall t \in X$ and $\alpha \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.13 [16] Let $R = (R_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F})$ and $B = (B_{T,I,F}, \upsilon_{T,I,F})$ are two NCSs of X and Y respectively. The Cartesian product $R \times B = (X \times Y, R_{T,I,F} \times B_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F} \times \upsilon_{T,I,F})$ is defined by $(R_{T,I,F} \times B_{T,I,F})(t * \alpha, t * \beta) = \text{rmin}\{R_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), B_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\}$ and $(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \upsilon_{T,I,F})(t * \alpha, t * \beta) = \text{max}\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \upsilon_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\}$, where $R_{T,I,F} \times B_{T,I,F} \mid X \times Y \rightarrow D[0,1]$ and $\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \upsilon_{T,I,F} \mid X \times Y \rightarrow [0,1] \forall (t, t) \in X \times Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.14 [16] A neutrosophic cubic subset $R \times F = (X \times Y, R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})$ is called a NCNID if satisfies these conditions:

1. $(R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(0,0) \geq (R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((t * \alpha), (t * \beta))$ and $(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(0,0) \leq (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((t * \alpha), (t * \beta)) \forall (t, t) \in X \times Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$.
2. $(R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(t_1 * \alpha, t_1 * \beta) \geq \text{rmin}\{(R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((t_1 * \alpha, t_1 * \beta) * (t_2 * \alpha, t_2 * \beta)), (R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(t_2 * \alpha, t_2 * \beta)\}$.
3. $(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(t_1 * \alpha, t_1 * \beta) \leq \max\{(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((t_1 * \alpha, t_1 * \beta)(t_2 * \alpha, t_2 * \beta)), (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(t_2 * \alpha, t_2 * \beta)\}$ and $R \times F$ is closed normal ideal if it satisfies 2, 3, and 4. $(R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (t_1 * \alpha, t_1 * \beta)) \geq (R_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(t * \alpha, t * \beta)$ and $(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (t * \alpha, t * \beta)) \leq (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(t * \alpha, t * \beta) \forall (t_1, t_1)$ and $(t_2, t_2) \in X \times Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.15 [9] Let $\tilde{F}_k = (A_{e_i}, \Lambda_{e_i})$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set, where Y is subalgebra. Then \tilde{F}_k is NSCMSU under binary operation $*$ where $t_1, t_2 \in Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$ if it fulfills these conditions:

$$A_{e_i}^0((t_1 * \alpha) * (t_2 * \beta)) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^0(t_1 * \alpha), A_{e_i}^0(t_2 * \beta)\} \text{ and } \lambda_{e_i}^0((t_1 * \alpha) * (t_2 * \beta)) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^0(t_1 * \alpha), \lambda_{e_i}^0(t_2 * \beta)\}.$$

3. γ -Multiplication of Neutrosophic Cubic Normal Ideal and Closed Normal Ideal

Definition 3.1. Let $Hb = (H_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F})$ be a NCS of X and $\gamma \in [0,1]$. An object of the form $Hb_\gamma^M = ({}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}^{Hb}, {}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}^{Hb})$ is called neutrosophic cubic γ multiplication of Hb X if it fulfills following axioms:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^M_\gamma H_T^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot H_T^{Hb}(x), & {}^M_\gamma \lambda_T^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot \lambda_T^{Hb}(x), \\ {}^M_\gamma H_I^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot H_I^{Hb}(x), & {}^M_\gamma \lambda_I^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot \lambda_I^{Hb}(x), \\ {}^M_\gamma H_F^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot H_F^{Hb}(x), & {}^M_\gamma \lambda_F^{Hb}(x) &= \gamma \cdot \lambda_F^{Hb}(x). \end{aligned}$$

For convinience we use ${}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}^{Hb} = \gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}^{Hb}(x)$ and ${}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}^{Hb} = \gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}^{Hb}(x)$.

Theorem 3.1 A γ -multiplication of NCCNID of B-algebra X is also a γ -multiplication of NCMSU of X .

Proof. Suppose $Hb = \{H_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F}\}$ be a NCCNID of X , then for any $t \in X$, we have ${}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) = \gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) \geq \gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha)$ and ${}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) = \gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \alpha)) \leq \gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha)$. Now by N4, N6, and through proposition 3.3 of article M subalgebra, we know that ${}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) = \gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) \geq \gamma \cdot \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) * (0 * (t * \beta))), H_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \beta))\} = \gamma \cdot \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), H_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \beta))\} \geq \gamma \cdot \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), H_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{\gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \gamma \cdot H_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{{}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), {}^M_\gamma H_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\}$ and ${}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) = \gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) \leq \gamma \cdot \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(((t * \alpha) * (t * \beta)) * (0 * (t * \beta))), \lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \beta))\} = \gamma \cdot \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (t * \beta))\} \leq \gamma \cdot \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\} = \max\{\gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), \gamma \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\} = \max\{{}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \alpha), {}^M_\gamma \lambda_{T,I,F}(t * \beta)\}$. Hence, γ MNCCNID is γ MNCMSU of X .

Proposition 3.1 Every γ -multiplication of NCCNID is a γ -multiplication NCNID but the converse is not true in general.

Theorem 3.2 The R-intersection of any set of γ MNCNIDs of X is also a γ MNCNID of X.

Proof. Let $H_i = \{H_{T,I,F}^i, \lambda_{T,I,F}^i\}$, where $i \in k$, be a γ MNCNID of X and $t, \mathfrak{t} \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(0) &= \text{rinf } M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i(0) = \text{rinf } H_{T,I,F}^i(0) \cdot \gamma \\ &\geq \text{rinf } H_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \cdot \gamma = \text{rinf } M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \\ &= (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) \\ &\Rightarrow (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(0) \geq (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(0) &= \text{sup } M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(0) = \text{sup } \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(0) \cdot \gamma \\ &\leq \text{sup } \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \cdot \gamma = \text{sup } M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \\ &= (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) \\ &\Rightarrow (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(0) \leq (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha), \end{aligned}$$

now

$$\begin{aligned} (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) &= \text{rinf } M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) = \text{rinf } H_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \cdot \gamma \\ &\geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), H_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\}\} \cdot \gamma \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf } H_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \cdot \gamma, \text{rinf } H_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) \cdot \gamma\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf } M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), \text{rinf } M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{(\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)((\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \Rightarrow (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) \geq \\ &\text{rmin}\{(\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), (\cap M_{\gamma}^i H_{T,I,F}^i)(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) &= \text{sup } M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) = \text{sup } \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(t * \alpha) \cdot \gamma \\ &\leq \text{sup}\{\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\}\} \cdot \gamma \\ &= \max\{\text{sup } \lambda_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \cdot \gamma, \text{sup } \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) \cdot \gamma\} \\ &= \max\{\text{sup } M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), \text{sup } M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \\ &= \max\{(V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(t * \alpha) \leq \max\{(V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)((t * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), (V M_{\gamma}^i \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(0), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)$, so ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) \leq {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)$.

Theorem 3.6. Let ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}$ of $\mathbb{H} = \{H_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F}\}$ is a NCNID of X . $\forall \mathfrak{t}, \mathfrak{t} \in X$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$, then \mathbb{H} is a NCMSU of X .

Proof. Assume that ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}$ is a NCNID of X , $\forall \mathfrak{t}, \mathfrak{t} \in X$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$. Then $\mathfrak{x} \cdot H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \geq \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \beta) * ((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(0), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}, H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) \cdot \mathfrak{x}\} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} \Rightarrow H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \geq \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\}$ and $\mathfrak{x} \cdot \lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \leq \max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \beta) * ((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(0), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \leq \max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}, \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) \cdot \mathfrak{x}\} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} \Rightarrow \lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \leq \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\}$. Hence, $\mathbb{H}\{H_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F}\}$ is a NCMSU of X .

4. \mathfrak{y} -MULTIPLICATION UNDER HOMOMORPHISM

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ is a homomorphic mapping of PS -algebra. If ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}$ of $\mathbb{H} = (H_{T,I,F}, \lambda_{T,I,F})$ is a NCNID of Y , then pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}) = (\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}))$ of ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}$ under Γ of X is a NCNID of X .

Proof. For all $\mathfrak{t} \in X$ and $\alpha \in [0,1]$, $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \leq H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(0)$ and $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \geq \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(0)$.

Let $\mathfrak{t}, \mathfrak{t} \in X$, $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \geq \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * \Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\}$ and $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \leq \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * \Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \max\{\Gamma^{-1}(\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), \Gamma^{-1}(\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)) \cdot \mathfrak{x}\} = \max\{\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\}$. Hence, $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}) = (\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}))$ is a NCNID of X .

Theorem 4.2. Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphic mapping of B -algebra. If ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}_i$ of $\mathbb{H}_i = (H_{T,I,F}^i, \lambda_{T,I,F}^i)$ is a NCNID of Y where $i \in k$, then the pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in k} {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}_i) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in k} {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}^i), \Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in k} {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}^i))$ is a NCNID of X .

Proof. We can prove this theorem through Theorem 3.2 and Theorem 4.1.

Theorem 4.3. Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ is an epimorphic mapping of B -algebra. Then ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F})$ is a NCNID of Y , if pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}) = (\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}))$ of ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\mathbb{H}$ under Γ of X is a NCNID of X

Proof. For any $\mathfrak{t} \in Y$, $\mathfrak{t} \in X$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$ such that $(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) = \Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)$. Then ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = \Gamma^{-1}(H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \geq \Gamma^{-1}(H_{T,I,F})(0) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = H_{T,I,F}(0) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(0)$ and ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) = \Gamma^{-1}(\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \leq \Gamma^{-1}(\lambda_{T,I,F})(0) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(0)) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = \lambda_{T,I,F}(0) \cdot \mathfrak{x} = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(0)$.

Assume $\mathfrak{t}_1, \mathfrak{t}_2 \in Y$. Then $\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) = \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta$ and $\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha) = \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta$ for some $\mathfrak{t}_1, \mathfrak{t}_2 \in X$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$. Thus ${}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) = \Gamma^{-1}(H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x} \geq \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}, \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}\} = \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}, \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{y}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{x}\}$

$\alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)\}. \mathfrak{r} = \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))), H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))\}. \mathfrak{r} =$
 $\text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * \Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), H_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))\} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}. \mathfrak{r} =$
 $\text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)). \mathfrak{r}, H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\} \quad \text{and}$
 ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha)) = \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) = \Gamma^{-1}(\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha). \mathfrak{r} \leq \max\{\Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), \Gamma^{-1}({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)\}. \mathfrak{r} =$
 $\max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))\}. \mathfrak{r} =$
 $\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * \Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\Gamma(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha))\} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}. \mathfrak{r} =$
 $\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)). \mathfrak{r}, \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}.$
 Hence, ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})$ is a NCNID of Y .

5. \mathfrak{r} -MULTIPLICATION OF CARTESIAN PRODUCT

Theorem 5.1. Let ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})$ and ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})$ are NCNIDs of X and Y respectively. Then ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F}$ is a neutrosophic cubic normal ideal of $X \times Y$.

Proof. For any $(\mathfrak{t}, \mathfrak{t}) \in X \times Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$. We have $({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})(0,0) = \mathfrak{r}. (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(0,0) =$
 $\mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(0), F_{T,I,F}(0)\} \geq \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha). \mathfrak{r}, F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} =$
 $\text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta)$ and $({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})(0,0) =$
 $\mathfrak{r}. (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(0,0) = \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(0), \mu_{T,I,F}(0)\} \leq \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha). \mathfrak{r}, \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} =$
 $\max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta).$

Let $(\mathfrak{t}_1, \mathfrak{t}_1), (\mathfrak{t}_2, \mathfrak{t}_2) \in X \times Y$ and $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$. Then $({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = \mathfrak{r}. (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta)\} \geq \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{\text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)\}, \text{rmin}\{F_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}\} = \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{\text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), F_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta))\}, \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}\} = \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{(H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), (\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta))\} = \text{rmin}\{(H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)). \mathfrak{r}, (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \text{rmin}\{({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}R_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}R_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\} \quad \text{and} \quad ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = \mathfrak{r}. (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) = \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha), \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta)\} \leq \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), \lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)\}, \max\{\mu_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}\} = \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha)), \mu_{T,I,F}((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta))\}, \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}\} = \mathfrak{r}. \max\{(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha), (\mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta))\} = \max\{(\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)). \mathfrak{r}, (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \max\{({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})((\mathfrak{t}_1 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_1 * \beta) * (\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)), ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t}_2 * \alpha, \mathfrak{t}_2 * \beta)\}. Hence, ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F}$ is a neutrosophic cubic normal ideal of $X \times Y$.$

Theorem 5.2. Let ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F})$ and ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F}, {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})$ are two \mathfrak{r} -multiplications of neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideals of X and Y respectively. Then ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F}$ is a NCCNID of $X \times Y$.

Proof. By Proposition 3.1 and Theorem 5.1, ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F}$ is NCNID. Now, $({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta)) = (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta)). \mathfrak{r} = (H_{T,I,F} \times F_{T,I,F})(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), 0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)). \mathfrak{r} = \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)), F_{T,I,F}(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \geq \mathfrak{r}. \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \text{rmin}\{H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha). \mathfrak{r}, F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \text{rmin}\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}H_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}F_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta) \quad \text{and} \quad ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta)) = (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})((0,0) * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta)). \mathfrak{r} = (\lambda_{T,I,F} \times \mu_{T,I,F})(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), 0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta)). \mathfrak{r} = \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \alpha)), \mu_{T,I,F}(0 * (\mathfrak{t} * \beta))\} \leq \mathfrak{r}. \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = \max\{\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha). \mathfrak{r}, \mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta). \mathfrak{r}\} = \max\{{}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha), {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F}(\mathfrak{t} * \beta)\} = ({}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\lambda_{T,I,F} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\mu_{T,I,F})(\mathfrak{t} * \alpha, \mathfrak{t} * \beta). Hence, ${}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{Hb} \times {}^M_{\mathfrak{S}}\text{F}$ is a neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideal of $X \times Y$.$

6. Conclusion

In this paper, the notion of τ -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set was introduced and τ -multiplication was studied by several useful results. This study will provide the base for further work like t-neutrosophic soft cubic and intuitionistic soft cubic set etc

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